

1 **Current methods for the evaluation of chemical contamination**
2 **risks from abandoned coal and lead-zinc mine lands: Protocol for**
3 **a systematic evidence map**

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23

24 **ABSTRACT**

25 **Background:** Abandoned mine lands (AMLs) pose significant environmental risks by releasing
26 contaminants that can adversely affect plants, animals, and human health, especially in highly
27 contaminated areas. Guidance exists on conducting contaminated land risk assessments. Understanding
28 and documenting changes in the methods used for AMLs risk assessments can help identify gaps and
29 advances in practice, influencing future research, policy, and remediation efforts.

30 **Methods:** The study aims to synthesise current methods for characterising the risks of chemical
31 contamination associated with AMLs, with a focus on coal and lead-zinc mines due to their enduring
32 toxic legacies.

33 **Search Strategy:** Searches will be conducted across six electronic databases, including Web of
34 Science, Scopus, ScienceDirect, PubMed, Academic Search Complete, and Business Source Premier
35 (via EbscoHost), as well as grey literature sources.

36 **Eligibility Criteria:** Eligible studies must include primary research assessing chemical risks from
37 abandoned coal and lead-zinc mines. They must have assessed or measured risks associated with
38 chemicals on ecological or human receptors at the community, population, or individual level.

39 **Screening & Data Extraction:** Studies retrieved from literature searches will undergo title and abstract
40 screening, followed by a full-text assessment for eligibility. Following pilot screening, a single reviewer
41 will screen all articles independently, with a second reviewer verifying accuracy for 20% of the sources.
42 Data on methods for exposure assessment, including exposure modelling where relevant, selected safety
43 thresholds, risk characterisation will be extracted from all eligible studies. Accuracy of the extraction
44 process will also be verified by a second reviewer for 20% of the eligible articles.

45 **Study Analysis & Reporting:** Collated methods will be categorised to establish current practices and
46 compared with existing guidance to assess alignment and deviations. Results will be summarised
47 narratively and presented in interactive, publicly accessible visualisations.

48

49 **Keywords:** Abandoned mine lands, contaminants, risk assessment, toxicity.

50

51 [Authors' contributions:](#)

52 Joanne McPhie: Methodology and Resources. Olwenn V. Martin: Conceptualisation, Data curation, Funding
53 acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Software, Supervision, Validation, and Writing - review &
54 editing. Rakesh Kanda: Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Validation, and Writing - review
55 & editing. Trevor Hoey: Writing - review & editing. Ushemegebe R. Ekhareafo: Conceptualisation, Data curation,
56 Funding acquisition, Methodology, Validation, Writing - original draft, and Writing - review & editing.

57 This systematic evidence map was conceptualised by URE under the supervision of OVM. URE contributed her
58 expertise in environmental geology and chemical contamination, OVM in environmental sciences, toxicology,
59 chemical risk assessment and systematic evidence maps. RK lent his knowledge in analytical chemistry, and TH
60 offered expertise in contaminant dispersal in rivers through sediment transport and consequent environmental
61 impacts. JMP provided expertise in information systems. The search strategy was developed by URE, with input

62 and discussions from OVM and JMP. Eligibility criteria were developed by URE and OVM and piloted by URE,
63 OVM and RK. The draft data extraction template was prepared by URE, revised following inputs from OVM and
64 was piloted by URE and OVM. URE prepared the final draft of the protocol. All co-authors reviewed successive
65 versions of the protocol.

66

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71 [Competing Interests](#)

72 Authors have no competing interests. Complete declarations of interest for all co-authors are provided.

73

74 [Data availability statement](#)

75 Supplementary materials relating to this protocol can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14246187>

76 Background

77 Historically, the mining of natural resources did not always adequately consider impacts on health and
78 the environment (Gallart, 2017; Macklin et al., 2023). Mining activities vary greatly in method and
79 scale, including artisanal and industrial mining at small, medium, or larger scales, and open-pit, surface,
80 and underground methods. Many past mining operations lacked planning and were conducted
81 haphazardly, leaving behind a legacy of contaminated mine lands (Hasheela et al., 2015). Mine closure,
82 the planned or unplanned cessation of a mining operation, is a critical phase in the mining life cycle that
83 ought to be designed and included in the mine operation plan (De Graff, 2020). Properly designed
84 closure aims to restore land for ecological or alternative uses, ensure ecological and human safety, and
85 reduce environmental and social damage (De Graff, 2020; ICMM, 2019, 2021; Laurence, 2006). The
86 costs of mine closure are significant and, as a result, mine lands are often left unattended when mineral
87 resources are exhausted (ICMM, 2019, 2021). An abandoned mine refers to a former mine where
88 extraction and processing occurred that is no longer in operation and for which there is no responsible
89 entity to finance the cost of remediation or restoration. By contrast, abandoned mine lands (AMLs)
90 include waste repository sites, water bodies, and surrounding watersheds where extraction,
91 beneficiation, or processing of mineral resources has occurred. AMLs are also defined by the absence
92 of responsible parties to oversee their management or restoration (EA, 2008; Holmes & Stewart, 2011;
93 US EPA, 2024). The difference is in their scope and structure, both characterised by a range of
94 landscape features that may include stagnant pond water, mine water, waste rocks, tailings
95 impoundments, areas impacted by smelter plumes, abandoned equipment, and structures. Many mining
96 companies ceased operations before environmental regulations governing the management of mines
97 came into force in their respective jurisdiction. Hence, governments are often left with the legacies of
98 abandoned mines and responsibility for their rehabilitation (Coelho et al., 2011; Hasheela et al., 2015).
99 Globally, over a million abandoned mines (Figure 1) have been identified, including shafts, adits, and
100 alluvial surface mines (Coelho et al., 2011).

Figure 1: Estimated number of AMLs in some regions and countries 1. (BML, 2017); 2. (Ashby & van-etten, 2021); 3. (EEA, 2004); 4. (Hughes, 2024a); 5. (Martínez-López et al., 2021); 6. (Tyson, 2020); 7. (Hans, 2021); 8. (MECD, 2022); 9. (Venkateswarlu et al., 2016)

Abandoned mines are significant sources of persistent contamination, primarily due to heavy metals, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and natural radionuclides (Gopinathan et al., 2023). These pollutants are released through mine waste, tailings, acid mine drainage (AMD), and other environmental processes (Iatan, 2021). Heavy metals such as arsenic, lead, cadmium, and chromium persist in these sites, accumulating in waste and tailings, with increased mobility under acidic conditions (Han et al., 2023; Wolkersdorfer & Mugova, 2022). PAHs are carcinogenic and mutagenic, partially persistent in anaerobic or low oxygen conditions, and bind strongly to sediments and soil (Bukowska et al., 2022; Li et al., 2019; Venkatraman et al., 2024). Natural radionuclides, including uranium, thorium, and radon, pose radiotoxic risks through inhalation or ingestion, depending on the environmental conditions (Momčilović et al., 2013; Paul et al., 2022). These contaminants migrate through soil, water, and air, influencing surrounding ecosystems and necessitating detailed environmental and health assessments to guide remediation efforts.

AMD is a major source of contamination, affecting watercourses globally. Many specific sites have been described in the literature e.g., Tinto-Odiel rivers in southern Spain (Grande et al., 2003), surface waters of Gujiao and Gyama valley in China (Huang et al., 2010; Ping et al., 2017), and Blyde river catchment in South Africa (Selebalo et al., 2021). Over 23,000 km of contaminated rivers have been recorded in the United States (Cravotta et al., 2010; Gammons et al., 2010). Additionally, the release of heavy metals and PAHs into surrounding soils and sediments can cause extensive pollution, with high contamination levels recorded in rivers and soils (Han et al., 2023; Hughes, 2024a; Sartorius, 2024; Wolkersdorfer & Mugova, 2022). In coal AMLs, PAHs contribute to environmental and health risks,

127 with severe implications for aquatic ecosystems (Li et al., 2019). Moreover, the dispersion of pollutants
128 through surface runoff, groundwater leaching, and sediment transport exacerbates the contamination of
129 water and soil resources (Candeias et al., 2015; Patel et al., 2024).

130

131 The persistence of pollutants such as heavy metals and organic contaminants in the environment poses
132 ongoing risks to both humans and ecosystems (Sartorius, 2023), especially when combined, leading
133 to the loss of plant and animal species (Coelho et al., 2011; Venkateswarlu et al., 2016; Worlanyo &
134 Jiangfeng, 2021). Studies of abandoned lead-zinc mines reveal their long-term health effects (Chukwu
135 & Obiora, 2023; Obiora et al., 2016; Sartorius et al., 2022; Son et al., 2019; US EPA, 2000b),
136 highlighting the need for targeted remediation and risk management (Naidu et al., 2019; Rouhani et al.,
137 2023).

138

139 Assessing these risks is critical to preventing long-term environmental damage and protecting public
140 health. Risk can be defined as the product of the impact and the probability of that event occurring. In
141 this context, risk is the potential for harmful impacts resulting from exposure to environmental stressors
142 that could be physical, geological, biological, or chemical entities (Bartell, 2008; US EPA, 1998).
143 Chemical risk assessment (CRA) typically consists of the comparison of an exposure level, the
144 concentration of the chemical of interest in a given compartment (exposure assessment), with the
145 corresponding safety threshold, derived from knowledge of the toxicity of that chemical (hazard
146 assessment). CRA for AMLs essentially aligns with frameworks used in contaminated land assessment
147 and follows a structured four-step evaluation involving hazard identification, hazard assessment,
148 exposure assessment, and risk characterisation (ISO, 2017; OECD, 2021; UK EA, 2020; US EPA, 2022;
149 WHO, 2010). Whilst they may vary according to contextual environmental factors, the hazardous
150 properties of a chemical, such as mobility, toxicity, persistence, and bioaccumulation are intrinsic to a
151 substance's chemical structure and physico-chemical properties. CRA in AMLs typically use existing
152 safety thresholds from regulatory hazard evaluation. Whilst a reference for that safety threshold is given,
153 the process to select it is rarely reported. Accordingly, for this systematic evidence map, we will capture
154 the sources of the hazard thresholds and, when available, the process and rationale for their selection.
155 CRA in AMLs typically begins with site characterisation, involving a desk study to review historical
156 data, including Earth Observation data, and a walkover survey to develop an initial Conceptual Site
157 Model (CSM). This model identifies potential contaminant sources, exposure pathways, and receptors
158 at risk. This informs the sampling strategy, sample preparation, and laboratory analysis to identify and
159 quantify contaminants in line with established standards and procedures (ISO, 2018; UK EA, 2020; US
160 EPA, 2000a). We aim to capture exposure assessment methods specific to the AML context. Risk
161 characterisation of AMLs is necessary to evaluate individual sites, prioritise those requiring
162 remediation, and develop sustainable, site-specific mitigation plans to protect affected receptors. This
163 risk management stage is beyond the scope of this systematic evidence map (SEM).

164 1.1 Rationale

165 This evidence map aims to identify and synthesise methods used to assess and evaluate chemical risks
166 from AMLs. This study seeks to identify current practices as reported in the peer-reviewed literature.
167 Although many national and international guidelines are available (e.g. CCME, 2016; ICMM, 2007,
168 2016; ISO, 2017; NEPM, 2014; UK EA, 2020; US EPA, 2000a; WHO, 2010), most are general (for
169 contaminated lands overall) and not tailored to AML-specific complexities. In contrast, academic
170 research frequently applies more tailored and nuanced, site-specific assessments.

171 AMLs present unique challenges due to their diverse contaminant sources, multiple pathways, diffuse
172 pollution, and persistent environmental legacies. The complex interactions of physical, chemical, and
173 environmental hazards (BML, 2017; DEP, 2015; Fields, 2003; Lottermoser, 2010; Venkateswarlu et
174 al., 2016) are associated with the nature of mining operations, the type of mine structures, and long-
175 term legacy impacts (Hufty, 2019; Jain et al., 2016), which amplify overall risk. As recognised by
176 ICMM (2007), traditional RA and guidance fail to consider the specificities of metals, a major problem
177 in AMLs (ICMM, 2007). They require additional layers of considerations, such as mine infrastructure,
178 waste repositories, geotechnical instability of hillslopes and tailings dams, river mobility, and the
179 chronic effects of AMD. Consequently, the scope of contaminants studied, the sampling strategies,
180 analytical methods, exposure models, specific sources, multiple pathways, contaminant fate and
181 transport models, and specific receptors typically considered in CRAs of AMLs may differ from
182 guidance that applies to contaminated land more generally.

183 Furthermore, CRA methods for AMLs need to be able to cope with increased complexity resulting from
184 climate change and increased anthropogenic pressures. Accounting for multiple chemical stressors ,
185 mixture risk assessment, and considering the effects of changing magnitude and/or frequency of
186 extreme events, sea-level rise, and other consequences of climate change, is required as these factors
187 may modify exposure and therefore risks (Marras et al., 2022). For instance, extreme rainfall and rising
188 temperatures can accelerate AMD formation, enhance contaminant mobility, and widen pollutant
189 dispersion (Anawar, 2013; Jacqueline et al., 2021; Li et al., 2024). Additionally, climate-driven impacts,
190 including erosion, permafrost thaw, altered hydrology, and land instability (Bulovic et al., 2024; Palma
191 et al., 2019; Santos et al., 2019), threaten ecosystems and human health (Grajal-Puche et al., 2024;
192 Hughes, 2024a). A case from Kam Kotia AML in Canada highlights that in 2012, rapid snowmelt
193 caused a tailings dam breach, releasing contaminated water and sediment into the surrounding
194 environment (MacMillan et al., 2021).

195 Some regulatory updates now reflect these emerging concerns. For example, the UK's updated guidance
196 (UK EA, 2020) mandates that climate change impacts be considered from project inception through
197 long-term monitoring of contaminated land.

198 A bibliographic search for literature reviews synthesising methods of risk assessment specific to
199 chemical contamination from AMLs yielded no comprehensive results. This suggests a notable gap in
200 efforts to consolidate guidance in relation to risk from legacy mine contamination. A SEM can help
201 synthesise current methods, and highlight where guidance is lacking, and how current practice deviates
202 from established guidance.

203 This SEM aims to provide a foundational tool for improving AML-specific risk assessments and
204 guiding future research, policy, and remediation efforts. Consolidating key insights, it seeks to provide
205 a valuable reference for organisations, policymakers, researchers, and practitioners involved in
206 addressing chemical risks from AMLs.

207 The literature search timeframe encompasses developments over the past two decades, capturing
208 recent advances in AMLs risk assessment methods.

209 1.2 Systematic Evidence Map (SEM)

210 Evidence maps follow transparent and replicable methods, including the formulation of structured
211 research questions, comprehensive and reproducible literature searches, and standardised data
212 extraction procedures (James et al., 2016; Wolffe et al., 2019). This ensures consistency and reliability,
213 making evidence maps particularly valuable for informing environmental policy, prioritising future
214 research, and guiding mitigation strategies (James et al., 2016; Miake-Lye et al., 2016).

215 They are used to systematically catalogue and visualise the breadth and characteristics of research in a
216 given field (Miake-Lye et al., 2016). In the context of environmental risk assessment, particularly in
217 complex domains such as chemical contamination from abandoned mines, evidence maps help organise
218 diverse sources of information across geographic regions, contaminant types, pathways, and receptors,
219 amongst other factors (James et al., 2016). Unlike traditional systematic reviews that aim to synthesise
220 outcomes, evidence maps focus on providing a high-level overview of the existing evidence, its areas
221 of concentration, and significant gaps (Snilstveit et al., 2016). They do not necessarily include or
222 necessitate a critical appraisal of individual studies, and such a step has not been included in the
223 proposed work.

224 1.3 Scope

225 Globally, the most mined minerals by weight are coal, iron ore, aluminium (bauxite), copper, chromium,
226 zinc, titanium, and lead (Casey, 2018; LePan, 2020; Venditti, 2023) with over 7 billion tonnes of coal
227 (IEA News, 2023) and 17 million tonnes of lead-zinc mined each year (Venditti, 2023). Among these,
228 coal and lead mines are of particular concern due to the significant and well-documented severe health
229 risks, especially those linked to exposure associated with legacy contamination from AMLs (Hughes,
230 2024b; Li & McDonald-Gillespie, 2020; Sartorius, 2023; US EPA, 2020). Hence, given their substantial
231 toxic legacies, and the environmental persistence, and the health and ecological impacts of associated

232 metals, lead-zinc mines are valuable case studies within the broader global context of AMLs
 233 contamination (Morgan, 2024; Rouhani et al., 2023; Sartorius, 2023, 2024; Tozsin et al., 2022; Wani et
 234 al., 2021). Accordingly, this evidence map will focus on methods of assessing risks from abandoned
 235 coal and lead-zinc mines as representative examples of AML cases.

236 Pb/Zn and coal AMLs may not fully capture the impacts of other abandoned metal and mineral mines,
 237 such as abandoned gold mines. As a result, all relevant methods may not be fully captured by focusing
 238 on Pb/Zn metals and coal mines. For example, because of the complex transformation processes of
 239 mercury (Alpers et al., 2005), abandoned mercury mines may require specific methods of risk
 240 assessment, which our approach would miss. This limitation is acknowledged, as reviewing all
 241 abandoned minerals/metal mines is impractical due to time and resource constraints. Nonetheless, this
 242 protocol has been carefully designed and may be adaptable to other types of AMLs.

243 This SEM seeks to answer the following question: What are the current methods for evaluating chemical
 244 risks from abandoned coal and lead-zinc mines? This has been articulated using a Population,
 245 Intervention, and Outcome (PIO) statement (Table 1).

246 Here, the Population refers to the types of AMLs being assessed, the Intervention refers to the chemical
 247 risk assessment methods applied, and the Outcome refers to the types of risks or effects identified as
 248 impacting ecological and/or human receptors.

249 *Table 1: Population, Intervention, and Outcome (PIO) statement of assessment practices relating to*
 250 *chemical risk from Abandoned Mine Lands*

What are the current methods for evaluating chemical risks from abandoned coal and lead-zinc mines?	
Population (types of AMLs)	Abandoned mine lands (mines that are no longer active, have been shut down, closed, forgotten, or have ceased operation). Only coal and lead-zinc mines; all other former mining activities are out of scope.
Intervention (methods of chemical risk assessment)	Chemical risk assessment practices; studies must include an evaluation of the chemical risks (comparing exposure levels with a safety threshold). Intermediary interventions include exposure assessment and/or modelling, and risk assessment and characterisation. Studies in which actual effects (realised risks) are monitored are within scope, while studies limited

	to exposure or hazard assessment or characterisation will not be considered.
Outcome (types of risk and effects identified for ecological and human receptors)	Risks and effects of chemicals associated with AMLs on ecological and human receptors
Time Frame	Peer-reviewed studies or grey literature published between the years 2000 to 2024.

251

252 2.0 Materials and Methods

253 This protocol was developed giving due consideration to the recommendations of the Conduct of
 254 Systematic Reviews in Toxicology and Environmental Health Research (COSTER) (Whaley et al.,
 255 2020). Deviations from the COSTER recommendations are documented in the supplementary material
 256 2.1. This protocol is reported following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-
 257 Analysis Protocols (PRISMA-P) guidelines (Moher et al., 2015; Shamseer et al., 2015). The checklist
 258 is provided in the supplementary material 2.2 (PRISMA-P Checklist).

259 2.1 Eligibility Criteria

260 The PIO statement in Table 1 was used as the starting point to articulate the eligibility criteria for
 261 inclusion in the SEM, with the following considerations:

262 **Population:** The focus is on abandoned coal and lead-zinc mines, as they represent an enduring toxic
 263 legacy with significant environmental and public health risks. Studies on other types of mines will be
 264 excluded, although the protocol may be adaptable for application to other abandoned mine types.

265 **Intervention:** This refers to the chemical risk assessment methods applied to evaluate risk. Initial pilot
 266 activities revealed that there is a large body of literature documenting chemical contamination in AMLs,
 267 but many studies stop short of conducting a chemical risk assessment. Including these studies, which
 268 primarily focus on analytical methods reporting concentrations of chemical contaminants, would add
 269 little value as they have already been extensively researched and reported over the years, and the effort
 270 required would exceed the resources available for this project. The scope was therefore refined and
 271 limited to studies that report or conduct a chemical risk assessment. Consequently, studies focusing
 272 solely on exposure or hazard assessments will be excluded. However, studies that evaluate actual
 273 impacts or harm, i.e., realised risks due to exposure to toxic chemicals from AMLs will be considered
 274 eligible while not specifically targeted by our search strategy.

275 **Outcome:** Types of risks and impacts identified for ecological and human receptors. Studies
 276 investigating quantitatively measurable toxicological effects on reproduction, growth, behaviour, or
 277 development on ecological and human receptors at the community, population, or individual level will

278 be included. Studies focusing on physical injury from engineering failures, hazards due to subsidence,
 279 or structural failures of tailings dams will be excluded. Studies focusing solely on exposure
 280 measurement, contaminant fate, transport, bioavailability, and bioaccumulation.

281 Study design: this evidence map is concerned with primary studies and reviews and meta-analyses will
 282 be excluded.

283 Timeframe: To comprehensively capture advances, applications, and persistent gaps in chemical risk
 284 assessment methods for AMLs, studies published between 2000 and 2024 will be included. This
 285 timeframe reflects a period of significant methodological development across international contexts.

286 *Table 2: Eligibility criteria*

Element	Statement	Inclusion	Exclusion
Population (types of AMLs)	Abandoned mine lands	Coal and lead-zinc mines. Abandoned open-pit or surface mines. Abandoned underwater and underground mines	Other types of AMLs, such as mercury and arsenic. Active mines, surface, open pit, underground, or underwater mines undergoing reclamation, rehabilitation, remediation, or restoration Other types of activities, such as active or abandoned quarries and smelting sites.
Intervention (Methods of chemical risk assessment)	Chemical risk assessment practices	Process: evaluation of the actual effects or potential impacts due to chemical exposures	Process: Studies focusing on inventory, prioritisation of sites, and chemical contamination without assessing the risk of such contamination.

		<p>Agents: organic and inorganic chemicals</p> <p>Exposure via water, sediment, soil, dust, air, biota (including food)</p> <p>Receptors: living organisms (humans and non-humans including micro-organisms, plants, vertebrate and invertebrate animals), and their systems (populations, communities, ecosystems)</p>	<p>Agents: nanominerals, macrominerals, microplastics, or organometallics</p> <p>Receptors: studies focusing on environmental media as endpoints without assessing associated risks to humans and non-human organisms.</p>
Outcome (types of risk and effects identified for ecological and human receptors)	Chemical risks and effects on ecological and human receptors	Evaluation of chemical/toxicological risks and impacts on reproduction, growth, behaviour, survival, or development in ecological and human receptors.	Physical injury due to natural or engineering hazards (subsidence), structural failure of tailing dams, hydrogeochemical behaviour, rock-water interaction.
Time Frame	Peer-reviewed studies and grey literature	Studies published between 2000 and 2024	Studies published before the year 2000

288 **2.2 Information sources**

289 The following six bibliographic databases will be searched for peer-reviewed articles using search
290 algorithms adequate for each database:

- 291 ● Web of Science
- 292 ● PubMed
- 293 ● Academic Search Complete and Business Source Premier (via EBSCOhost)
- 294 ● ScienceDirect
- 295 ● Scopus

296 In addition, manual searches of grey literature not indexed in the selected databases will be conducted,
297 targeting specific websites of government agencies, institutes, and other platforms, including:

- 298 ● International Council on Mining and Metals (ICMM)
- 299 ● US Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA)
- 300 ● UK Environment Agency (UK EA)
- 301 ● The International Organization for Standardization (ISO)
- 302 ● Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment (CCME)

303

304 **2.3 Search Strategy**

305 Pilot searches were conducted to iteratively develop the search strategy, with the assistance of an
306 information specialist (JMP) and insights from other systematic evidence maps related to environmental
307 studies. Initially, we planned to include all types of mines in our mapping. However, after conducting
308 preliminary searches, we realised this approach was unmanageable. We refined our focus to coal and
309 lead-zinc mines. During the piloting phase, we noticed many studies simply reported chemical
310 concentrations without contributing significantly to the research question. As a result, we decided to
311 specify our focus on studies assessing risk.

312 This approach addressed the challenge of identifying manuscripts specifically related to chemical risk
313 assessment methods from AMLs, as unspecific terms like "assessment" and "risk" yielded much
314 irrelevant research. The number of hits for synonyms related to the elements of the PIO statement was
315 recorded and combined using Boolean operators to ensure the search strategy maintained sensitivity
316 while achieving some level of specificity.

317 A general approach is shown in Table 3. This was tested across all listed databases, adjusting the search
318 strings to ensure appropriateness in retrieving relevant literature, except for ScienceDirect, which only
319 supports eight Boolean operators, restricting long, complex search algorithms. Truncation of words was
320 used with care. Proximity searches were run to find combined forms of terms. For example, Web of
321 Science uses the proximity operator NEAR/3 while Scopus's is w/3. A simplified search algorithm was
322 developed for ScienceDirect as follows:

323 *(Abandoned OR inactive) AND (coal OR lead OR zinc) AND Mine AND (Contaminant OR Pollution)*
 324 *AND "Risk Assessment"*

325 The use of adequate filters, such as article type and publication year, was also explored and applied.
 326 The results from piloting the search strategy, the complete search algorithms for each database, the
 327 compiled search strings, and the number of articles retrieved from each database are included in the
 328 supplementary materials 2.3 (search strategy). The sensitivity of the search strategy was assessed using
 329 a set of relevant articles identified during an initial review of the impacts of abandoned coal and lead-
 330 zinc mines. All selected articles were successfully retrieved using Web of Science, while 90% were
 331 also captured by Scopus and PubMed. This confirmed that our core search terms would be effective in
 332 retrieving key literature relevant to the evidence mapping.

333
 334 The term "historic" was initially omitted from the pilot search. To ensure that relevant articles were not
 335 missed, this term was later searched separately in combination with other key terms, as shown below:

336
 337 *(Historic) NEAR/3 (Coal OR Lead OR Zinc OR mine* OR exploitation OR site OR land) AND (Pollut**
 338 *OR contamin* OR chemical) AND (Risk)*

339
 340 Details of this additional pilot search and database-specific retrieval are provided in the supplementary
 341 material 2.3, and a flow diagram of the literature search results is presented in Supplementary materials
 342 2.4 .

343 Table 3: *General Search strategy combined with Boolean operators*

S/N	Keywords	Synonym
#1	Abandoned mines	(inactive OR historic OR orphan OR derelict OR forgotten OR disused OR deserted OR abandoned) NEAR/3 (Coal OR Lead OR Zinc OR mine* OR exploitation OR site OR land)
#2	Contamination	Pollut* OR contamin* OR chemical
#3	Risk	Risk

Total	#1 AND #2 AND #3	(inactive OR historic OR orphan OR derelict OR forgotten OR disused OR deserted OR abandoned) NEAR/3 (Coal OR Lead OR Zinc OR mine* OR exploitation OR site OR land) AND (Pollut* OR contamin* OR chemical) AND (Risk)
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344

345 2.4 Data management

346 The screening of the literature is managed using CADIMA, a user-friendly, free online tool established
 347 by the Julius Kühn Institut and the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence (Julius Kühn Institut,
 348 2017). The Mendeley Reference Manager (Elsevier, 2013) is used to manage manual searches while
 349 Citavi (Swiss Academic Software GmbH, 2024) is used for automatic retrieval of full-text that are
 350 accessible.

351 2.5 Selection Process/Screening

352 The defined eligibility criteria are applied to screen the merged list of references retrieved from each
 353 literature source after the duplicates have been removed. Screening is carried out in two stages. In the
 354 first stage, titles and abstracts are examined for relevance to the formulated question, with studies
 355 deemed irrelevant excluded. In the second stage, the full texts of the remaining studies from the first
 356 stage will be assessed for inclusion. The reasons for excluding studies at the full-text stage will be
 357 documented.

358 CADIMA facilitates a consistency check as a method of piloting the screening stage. Any
 359 disagreements between screeners were resolved through discussion, and agreed outcomes of these
 360 discussions were used to revise and clarify the eligibility criteria and ensure a consensus on their
 361 interpretation. The eligibility criteria were applied to 15% (randomised by CADIMA) of the merged
 362 reference list at the title and abstract level by two reviewers, OVM and URE, the outcome was assessed
 363 as “poor” by Cadima, mainly because differences between ‘included’ and ‘unclear’ decisions for each
 364 eligibility criterion at the title–abstract screening stage are recorded as discrepancies, though they do
 365 not materially affect the selection process. Additionally, URE first applied a stricter interpretation of
 366 the exclusion criteria, leading to some articles being marked as "excluded" when they should have been
 367 rated "unclear". A common example was when the title or abstract referred to AML without specifying
 368 the type of mine. All discrepancies from this pilot stage were resolved through discussion.

369 URE will screen the remaining articles independently, with an overlap of 20% of retrieved articles
 370 screened independently in duplicate by OVM as a quality control step. Any disagreements will be
 371 discussed as soon as they arise and resolved by consensus to ensure a consistent interpretation of

372 eligibility criteria and avoid drift. If the rate of discrepancies in inclusion-exclusion decisions becomes
373 too high (>1%), this will trigger duplicate screening of previously screened literature.

374 2.6 Data extraction

375 A data extraction template was developed and piloted to ensure consistency in the data extraction
376 process. The pilot extraction was conducted independently by two reviewers, URE and OVM.
377 Discrepancies in the extraction process were resolved through discussion and used to refine the data
378 extraction template and ensure that a consensus understanding of the process was reached. The piloted
379 data extraction sheet is available in supplementary materials 2.5 (Data Extraction Sheet-Pilot 1 and 2).
380 The data will be extracted from all included studies by a single reviewer (URE), and a sample of 25%
381 of the extracted data will be independently checked by OVM. The data extraction template is designed
382 to facilitate identification, documentation, and validation by a second reviewer. The finalised data
383 extraction template is included in supplementary materials 2.6 (Finalised data extraction template). A
384 coding strategy combining both deductive and inductive approaches was developed to guide the data
385 extraction process and is provided in the supplementary materials 2.7 (Code Book for Data Extraction).
386 This dual approach was selected to ensure both consistency and flexibility in capturing relevant
387 information across studies. The deductive component involved the predefined categorisation of
388 commonly encountered data types to standardise data recording. In parallel, the inductive component
389 was designed to allow for the identification and categorisation of emerging terms or concepts, during
390 the extraction process.

391 In brief, the following data will be extracted from all studies included during the full-text screening
392 stage:

- 393 ● Bibliographic metadata: Author(s), year, journal name, journal details (volume, issue, page),
394 article title and abstract, and source of funding.
- 395 ● Abandoned mined land details: study location (country, state, or county where the study was
396 carried out), mine name, information about the type of mine, method of mining, duration of
397 operation, and year of abandonment.
- 398 ● Exposure measurement (if relevant): Sample medium, sampling strategy, sample storage, and
399 preparation, sample volume (unit), method of chemical analysis, the limit of detection
400 (including unit), precision, accuracy, contaminant or pollutant name, CAS number,
401 information about the reported concentrations including the unit in the article, and other
402 contextual measurements.
- 403 ● Exposure modelling (if relevant): Source medium, pathway, target media, modelling method,
404 and reference used to model the exposure, chemical name, CAS number, and outcome.

- 405 ● Effect monitoring (if relevant): Taxonomic group, species, sampling strategy/method, sample
406 storage and preparation, sample size (unit), type and level of observed effect, measurement
407 methods, statistical significance, statistical methods, reported outcomes.
- 408 ● Risk characterisation: source, exposure pathway, receptor, risk characterisation method,
409 reference for the method used, the source of reference dose used (as well as notes on the
410 selection of the reference dose when this is reported), uncertainty factors, risk category,
411 outcome, consideration of mixtures.

412 This data extraction process is designed to systematically capture key components relevant to chemical
413 risk assessment at AMLs.

414 First, bibliographic metadata will be extracted to organise the studies included in this evidence map.
415 This information helps establish the context for the conduct of each study, including its authorship,
416 source of funding, publication details, abstract, and DOI.

417 The details of the abandoned mine lands, such as the location, type of mine, mining method, and
418 duration of abandonment, are crucial for evaluating environmental impacts. These factors influence the
419 pollution pathways and long-term risks associated with AMLs. Information about the mining history,
420 waste characteristics, and local geology is fundamental to predicting and assessing site-specific
421 environmental risks. The data from this section will help evaluate the applicability of different risk
422 assessment methods across specific contexts and support subset analyses of methodological differences.

423 Exposure assessment methods include details on the sampling strategy, storage and preparation of
424 samples, and the chemical analysis techniques used. Parameters such as the medium of exposure,
425 contaminant(s), and limit of detection data will help inform the applicability and performance of the
426 methods described. Exposure modelling is often essential for extrapolating measured concentrations of
427 contaminants in environmental media to concentrations in relevant pathways of exposure. Information
428 such as the exposure pathways, target media, and modelling methods helps to document current
429 methods used to predict human and ecological receptor exposure to chemical contaminants from AMLs.

430 Effect monitoring data, such as the taxonomic group, species involved, and the type and level of effects
431 observed, provide crucial evidence of the actual risks faced by receptors exposed to AML contaminants.
432 These data are particularly important for identifying realised risks and understanding the ecological and
433 human health consequences of chemical exposure.

434 Finally, data from risk characterisation methods, including references to the guidelines or method used,
435 and the incorporation of uncertainty factors, will help document the range of risk assessment methods
436 and applications across various exposure sources and routes. Also, information on whether mixture
437 risks are considered, along with the range of methods used, will be recorded.

438 The extraction of these data types will ensure that the evidence map captures a comprehensive overview
439 of current practices, which will allow us to query and document advancements, applications, and any
440 gaps in methods related to risk from AMLs. Piloting the data extraction has helped to establish
441 guidelines for maintaining a consistent format to extract data from included studies. The use of drop-
442 down menus also allows for categorisation, which will facilitate the data analysis. Following the
443 extraction process, the data will be cleaned, such as removing irrelevant symbols, units, or numbers,
444 before analysis and revisiting categorisation, as appropriate.

445 2.7 Data analysis and reporting

446 The outcome will address our objectives: identifying procedures, extracting relevant information for
447 evaluating chemical risks, and establishing current best practices related to chemical risk assessment of
448 AMLs.

449 The key characteristics of abandoned mines that have undergone risk assessment will be summarised
450 in tabular format, accompanied by a map visualising their geographic locations. Information related to
451 exposure measurement, exposure modelling, effect monitoring, and risk characterisation will also be
452 summarised in tables. This analysis aims to provide insights into both the diversity and frequency of
453 various methodologies and practices used to characterise chemical risks from AMLs. This will be
454 complemented by a critical narrative synthesis of the elements researchers identified as necessary in the
455 included studies.

456 The visualisation software Tableau (Salesforce Inc, 2025) allows for the creation of interactive
457 dashboards, enabling users to select subsets of data and easily view all relevant references and sources
458 of information. Tableau will be employed to illustrate quantitatively the use of categories of methods
459 from each risk assessment step and generate summary findings, highlighting key insights.

460

461 We will address the “current method” question for each risk assessment step through narrative analysis
462 and trend evaluation from the database. Tableau will help track changes over time, illustrating how
463 methods have evolved. This will be compared with guidance documents from organisations such as the
464 US EPA, UK EA, ICMM, and ISO to assess alignment and deviations. Through the data analysis, we
465 aim to identify scientific advancements in AML chemical risk assessment methods and highlight
466 improvements made over recent years. Identified gaps and limitations will also be documented.

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